

FEATURES OF THE PSYCHOLOGICAL DEVELOPMENT OF YOUTH AND THE DEVELOPMENT OF COGNITIVE PROCESSES.

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Annotation: *The woman in the company of the priestess was standing a step below him, her lips parted. However, today there are many women who have managed to get into the family and work, become a dear wife, a dear mother, an exemplary daughter-in-law, show themselves in their work, and become an honorable leader. But what is better if a woman is not a politician in power, but a politician in the family?!*

Kazakh women took part in all the affairs of society, except for the upbringing of the younger generation, and expressed their views. He was widely recognized as a wise adviser to Khans and sultans, batyrs and biys. This fact was in the center of attention of researchers of other nationalities

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The meaning of the world is in a woman," Yerman said, adding that in any era, in any people, a woman has a special place. In the Kazakh people, women were considered the song and fashion of life, the warmth of our home, the mind of men, and the caregiver of our children.

A woman is a wise girl, a wise daughter-in-law, a mother, a sister, a sister, a grandmother. A woman has a very responsible task. Nine months and ten days give life to humanity, expanding its narrow belly, soaking up the stone breast. "I don't know," he said. A woman was responsible for the upbringing of her offspring. There is a beautiful saying: "the child should be good." As for its origins, our ancestors paid special attention to the origin and dignity of their mothers and wives. This means that women have a high and responsible place in the process of reproduction.

In the Kazakh society, as well as in our noble religion, the girl was respected, respected and placed above all others. For example, a girl was placed as a guest in her house, a girl was banned from forty houses, the Prophet Muhammad (peace and blessings of Allaah be upon him) considered the child a gift from Allah, preferred the boy, and did not allow discrimination against the girl. After all, the girl's heart is soft, her soul is tender, she explained that tomorrow someone will be a companion, a guest in the right void. Also, in the nomadic farm there were men who raised their shanyrak when building a yurt, women who made a bed, and women who made a bed. Men who saw such advantages in women were protected by various laws. "I don't know," he said. For example: in Dulat Isabekov's story "The Passenger of the lungs", comparing the female substance to an unrecognized planet, scientists from all over the world together reveal the secrets of the world, but no science, genius can reveal the secrets of the female soul.

From an early age, the girl was brought up as a future wife, a dear mother, a white grandmother, as well as household chores, sewing, patchwork, morality, beauty, intelligence, and labor. "A giant is born of a mother," the word has a deep meaning. Almost all of our Khans and biys, brave heroes, poets and writers who ruled the ancient country were born from our mothers with Golden Hearts. The only example of our mothers who raised their children in a wise way is our mothers Domalak Ana, Ulzhan, Umai, Zere, Begim Ana, Shokan's grandmother Ayganym, who are known for their holiness.

Sonau ekinshi duniezhuzilik sogys zamanynda ayelder turli sharualarga aralasy, economy, onerkasip, zhenil onerkasip T.b salalaryn igere bastagan. Sol uakytan bastap aiel adamdar kogamdyk zhumystarga belsene katysyp, aiel adamdarda "er men aiel te kukyly" degen pikirler kalyptas bastady. Eri zhokta esti ayel ony zhoktatpai, barlyk zhumystardy ayel adamdar zhasai beretin darezhege zhetti.

Kazirgi kogamymyzda da ayel adamdardyn orny orasan zor. Ayel adamdardy bassy tulgalar katarynan, bizneste, ekonomikada, sayasatta baska da kasip salalarynda kezdestirip kalatynymyz ras. Olardyn sany kun sayyn artyp keledi desek te, otirik emes. Degenmen, "Altyn basty ayelden,

Baka basty yerkek artyk", - demekshi Alla tagala ayeldi ayel, yerkekti yerkek kylyp zharatkannan keyin, ayel adamdar kansha zherden sharua istep, er adamdarmen te kylymyz

dese de, er adamdardan mykty emes.

Kazak kogamyndagy ayel zaty yerin syilagan, yerinen bir saty tomen turgan. Degenmen, kazirgi tanda otbasyna da, zhumysyna da ulgerip, otbasynnda ayauly zhar, ardakty ana, ulgili kelin bolyp, zhumysynnda biik-biik belesterden korinip, abyroly bassy bop zhurgen aiel adamdary kanshama. Desek te, ayel – biliktegi sayasatker emes, otbasyndagi sayasatker bolsa kandai zhaksy?!

Kazak ayelderi urpak tarbiesinen ozge kogamnyn barlyk isterine katysyp, ozderinin kozkarastaryn bildirgen. Khandar men sultandardyn, batyrlar men bilerdin akylshy keneshileri retinde ken dalaga tanylgan. Munday zhayt ozge ult okilderi zertteushilerin nazarynda bolgan. Mysaly, zertteushi galym A.K.Gaines: "The Kyrgyz woman plays a big role not only as the mistress of the family, but also as a member of society. At Kyrgyz gatherings, women give their voice on an equal basis with men, especially on issues related to public needs. Sometimes even the opinion of women has some advantage over the opinion of men," [4,-76b] dep payymdagan.

All the facts of history indicate the special place of women in the life of the Kazakh people. Since gaining independence, the country has been taking concrete steps to accelerate the pace of integration into the world community, and the state has moved towards a reliable and harmonious development. At the same time, the priorities of gender policy have also undergone significant changes. Kazakhstan joined the UN Convention on the elimination of all forms of discrimination against women in 1998. The main directions of gender equality are defined in the gender equality strategy of the Republic of Kazakhstan for 2006-2016. "The implementation of the gender equality strategy in the Republic of Kazakhstan will contribute to creating conditions for women and men to realize their rights to life without discrimination on the basis of gender" [5,-4B]-the strategy sets the goal of implementing equal rights and equal opportunities for men and women.

In Kazakhstan, the issue of the role and place of women in society is at the disposal of the state leadership. In his speeches, the president of the Republic of Kazakhstan N. A. Nazarbayev repeatedly noted that the participation of women in the social context of the division of power, ownership, and status is logically integrated. On the one hand, the demographic growth of modern Kazakhstan's society is 6 million people. on the other hand, he noted that 40% of the country's budget consists of the economic activity of women entrepreneurs. Addressing the Central Asian Congress of business women (2012), N. A. Nazarbayev said: "Our task is to attract more women to politics and public activities. Based on my life experience, I have found that the responsibility of a woman in charge, a woman in charge, is increased, and she is honest...». Indeed, the women of Kazakhstan, especially their active part, have reached the highest limits of political consciousness and political culture, and they have become convinced of the importance of women in power structures.

Kazakstandyk kogam baska memleketter sekildi dasturli kundylyktaryn saktap, berik etuge talpynys zhasaud. "Kazakhstan-2050 Strategiyasi-kalyptaskan memlekettin zhana sayasi bagyty" atta Zholdauynda KR Presidenti N.A.Nazarbayev "Khalkymyz "Kyzdyn zholy zhishke" degenge erekshe man berip aytady. Boyzhetkennin zholy, kyzdyn zholy-kylday, ony uzuge bolmaydy. Boyzhetken, ayel zaty ardayim bizdin kogamnyn te kukyly mushesi, al ana-ony en ardakty tulgasy boldy. Biz aiel zatyna-anaga, jarga, kyzga degen kapysyz kurmetti kaita oraltuga tiispiz" [6,-45b] dep atap otti.

Kazirgi kazak aieli-kogam men memleket korki. Ayelder elimizde bolyp zhatkan barlyk kogamdyk-sayasi ozgeristerge, halykaralyk-diplomatiyalyk zhumystarga, kogamnyn buk tynys-tirshiligine belsen aralasyyp otyr. Olar bar kush-zhigerlerin ayamai yerlerman birge oz memleketti-bolashakka kadam baskan, azat ta zharkyn Kazakhstan ushin ayanbai enbek etude.

Adebietter

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